

THE ISSUE OF HUMAN RIGHTS AND FREEDOMS IN ISLAMIC LAW

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Annotatsiy. Maqolada islom huquqi tizimida inson huquq va erkinliklari masalasi tahlil qilinadi. Inson huquqlarini ta'minlash va muhofaza qilish islom huquqining asosiy maqsadlaridan biri ekanligi Qur'oni karim va Hadisi sharif asosida izohlanadi. Shu bilan birga, musulmon huquqida inson hayoti, din erkinligi, aql va mulk daxlsizligi, avlodni asrash kabi tamoyillar markaziy o'rinda turadi. Urf-odatlar va mahalliy an'analar bilan uyg'unlashgan holda shakllangan islom huquqi umuminsoniy qadriyatlar bilan hamohang bo'lib, zamonaviy inson huquqlari konsepsiyasi bilan qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Shu orqali Sharq davlatlaridagi huquqiy tizimlarda inson huquq va erkinliklariga oid normalarning shakllanishi va amal qilishi ko'rsatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Islom huquqi, inson huquqlari, erkinliklar, Shariat, Qur'on, Hadis, odat huquqi, umuminsoniy qadriyatlar, huquqiy tizim, Sharq davlatlari.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается проблема прав и свобод человека в системе исламского права. Подчеркивается, что обеспечение и защита прав человека является одной из главных целей исламского права, что находит свое отражение в Коране и Хадисах. Особое внимание уделяется таким принципам, как право на жизнь, свобода вероисповедания, неприкосновенность разума и имущества, защита будущих поколений. Исламское право, формируясь в гармонии с обычаями и местными традициями, соотносится с универсальными ценностями и подвергается сравнительному анализу с современной концепцией прав человека. В заключение показана роль исламского права в формировании и реализации норм о правах и свободах человека в правовых системах восточных государств.

Ключевые слова: исламское право, права человека, свободы, Шариат, Коран, Хадис, обычное право, универсальные ценности, правовая система, восточные государства.

Abstract. The article examines the issue of human rights and freedoms within the framework of Islamic law. It emphasizes that the protection and safeguarding of human rights is one of the main objectives of Islamic law, as reflected in the Qur'an and Hadith. Particular attention is given to the principles of the right to life, freedom of religion, the inviolability of intellect and property, and the protection of future generations. Formed in harmony with customs and local traditions, Islamic law aligns with universal values and is compared with the modern concept of human rights. The article also highlights the role of Islamic law in shaping and implementing human rights and freedoms in the legal systems of Eastern states.

Keywords: Islamic law, human rights, freedoms, Sharia, Qur'an, Hadith, customary law, universal values, legal system, Eastern states.

The processes of globalization and modernization taking place in today's world have inevitably influenced the socio-political, economic, spiritual, and legal life of Eastern states. In some of these countries, attempts are being made to harmonize Eastern and Western lifestyles, adopt modern legal norms, governance methods, and new interpretations regarding human rights. This is a manifestation of global integration. However, Islamic law still retains its influence and strength in many Eastern states, continuing to serve as the core of their political and legal doctrine. Consequently, the political and legal processes in these countries, including modernization and legal reforms, are primarily based on Islamic principles and jurisprudence.

In Islam, customary law is not rejected; rather, it relies on the traditions of the population and concepts of human rights that have been formed over centuries. As S. Jabborov, who specifically studied family relations in Islamic law, notes: "The strength and authority of Islamic laws lie in the fact that they are based not only on the Holy Qur'an and Hadith but also on customary norms

established over centuries, which protect the interests of individuals, every member of society, and the community as a whole. In Islamic law and customary norms, centuries-old universal values are generalized while taking into account local and national traditions.”

Therefore, “many Arab and European scholars emphasize that Islam has a universal character, and its normative rules are founded on a system of ‘faith and state,’ a unity of religion and law” (Abdul Aziz Amir, Muhammad Farukh an-Nabkhan, R. Charlot, etc.). They believe that in the Muslim world, legal norms are inseparably connected with moral norms. In the general normative prescriptions of fiqh, religious and “civil” legal rules are not distinguished, since the function of the state is to ensure that Muslims equally fulfill both the requirements of fiqh and religious obligations. However, in some Eastern countries, practices of adhering to local customs contrary to Islamic law can also be observed. For example, in Iran, Afghanistan, Yemen, and Jordan, customary courts still exist. This shows that Islamic law does not deny the consideration of local traditions in ensuring human rights and freedoms. On the contrary, it demonstrates an orientation toward expanding and safeguarding these rights by using local practices.

According to Islamic dogma, all human actions must be directed toward God, affirming His absoluteness and establishing His order on earth. A person must constantly feel the presence of a higher, supreme force—Allah. This doctrine is significant because it calls on everyone to live in unity and harmony, striving toward a common goal. The relationship between the whole and its parts, and their harmony, has always been a debated issue in legal scholarship.

In addition, “among the world’s religions, only Islam has a close connection with state and law. In this respect, Islamic legal ideology and Islamic law have always played the role of a binding factor.” Universality here is a phenomenon and concept relevant to jurisprudence and political science. From this perspective, Islamic law should be studied not only as a legal phenomenon but also as a socio-political one.

During the years of independence, legal scholars have conducted valuable research on human rights and freedoms in Islamic law, the development of national legal systems, the creation of a national legal identity, and the formation of the concept of nationhood, democratic rule of law, and civil society. In this regard, the works of academicians and doctors of law from the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan—such as Sh. Z. Urazayev, H. R. Rakhmonkulov, A. Saidov, H. B. Boboyev, Z. M. Islomov, E. H. Khalilov, A. Azizzhojaye, A. A. Agzamkhojaye, M. M. Fayziyev, U. Tojikhonov, G. Matkarimova, Kh. T. Odilqoriev, Kh. Mamatov, Z. Muqimov, R. Q. Qayumov, A. Sh. Juzjoniy, A. Rakhmonov and others—are noteworthy.

Their studies highlight the following approach to understanding human rights and freedoms in Islam:

1. To uncover retrospectively the role of historical-legal heritage in shaping human rights, especially the Islamic legal consciousness, including Sharia law, fiqh literature and practices, national statehood, socio-legal space, norms, moral-ethical values, customs, and traditions.
2. To acknowledge that no legal scholar has ignored these historical sources and political-legal ideas. This approach allows for the restoration of historical-legal heritage and the application of its positive ideas and principles in modern legal norms. Most importantly, these studies reveal that for centuries our people have preserved and practiced a vital socio-legal reality—justice, equality, fraternity, solidarity, purity, protection of the homeland, and patriotism. These values gave them faith in progress and in the triumph of goodness and justice.

As noted by the group of scholars led by Professor M. F. Fayziyev: “In Uzbek khanates, which were Muslim states based on Islamic law, monarchies prevailed. In regulating legal relations, the sources of law were: a) Islamic law; b) secular law in the form of decrees and edicts of rulers; and c) customary law. Regardless of this diversity of legal sources, Sharia law remained the main source of regulating social relations. Other sources were applied only if they did not contradict Sharia.” Thus, Sharia laws and norms represented the sole socio-legal reality of the khanates, and even the khan could

not arbitrarily alter them. This was primarily due to the dominance of Islamic ideology in social life. Although in the field of criminal law there were sometimes criteria and punishments contradicting Sharia, they were imposed by rulers in specific cases. However, this did not fundamentally alter the overall socio-legal norms and traditions. To change them would have required altering the entire Islamic world and its values.

To sum up, in the East, the phenomenon of law has traditionally been interpreted through the lens of spirituality, customs, and morality. Hence, elements of customary law still exist, and in some countries, they coexist with Islamic law. Islamic law, as a unique feature of Eastern jurisprudence, should be further studied to reveal the inherent characteristics of the socio-legal reality in the East.

In Eastern legal and socio-political thought, the specific term “human rights and freedoms in Islam” appears rarely. However, this does not mean that rights and freedoms were absent; rather, they were manifested in the legal relations of the state and in the development of societies within a certain socio-legal framework. So far, the phenomenon of human rights and socio-legal spaces in the East has not been sufficiently studied from a political perspective. Nevertheless, the topics addressed within Islamic law—such as the phenomenon of law, the functions and essence of the state, and the substantive nature of human behavior aimed at protecting one’s rights and freedoms—help us understand socio-legal reality more fully.

From the analyses presented, the following conclusions and recommendations can be made:

1. Human rights in Islamic law are broadly enshrined in the Qur’an, Hadith, and fiqh sources, with the primary goal of protecting life, intellect, faith, lineage, and property.
2. Studying the historical-legal heritage in depth provides a better understanding of Islamic perspectives on human rights and enables their application in modern legal systems.
3. Comparative legal analysis is needed to highlight similarities and differences between Islamic law and international human rights instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.
4. Incorporating principles of justice, equality, responsibility, and fairness from Islamic law into national legislation strengthens the humanistic spirit of legal reforms.
5. Practical insights can be gained by comparing the legal experiences of states such as Saudi Arabia, Iran, Egypt, and Uzbekistan.
6. Integrating Islamic principles of human rights with the requirements of modern democracy and civil society is essential.
7. International cooperation and the use of experiences from organizations such as the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, the UN, and UNESCO can enrich research and enhance the effectiveness of human rights protection in practice.

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